

RESO

WP2-2.3.3:

Data support for Preliminary Design. CFES Annual Energy Flow Sankey Diagrams

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Element	Description
Title	CFES Annual Energy Flow Sankey Diagrams
Creator	Dr Joseph Day
Subject	RESO 25 primary substation areas annual energy flows under future scenarios
Description	<p>These diagrams were created using a similar methodology to the earlier Sankey diagrams produced for the Coventry City Council. However, these are at a much higher level (i.e. less breakdown of each energy flow) and cover the RESO 25 primary substations area as opposed to just Coventry local authority.</p> <p>The units are GWh and the inputted data is based on the preliminary designs produced within the RESO project. These designs are under a Coventry Future Energy Scenarios framework which is broadly aligned with the Distribution Future Energy Scenarios. Three diagrams are presented: one for a 2018 baseline, one for a 2032 consumer transformation (CT) scenario where there is a high degree of electrification and one for a 2032 system transformation (ST) where there is a high degree of hydrogen and hydrogen-blended methane used in heavy transport and heating.</p>
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Smart Local Energy System Design

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